

AMERICAN ENGLISH AND BRITISH ENGLISH

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Alongside with globalization and intensive migration, rapidly changing economic, political and cultural background the consideration of issues of intercultural communication is becoming increasingly important. In the comparative studies, very often English is one of compared languages. Besides, English is a global language and the term “English as an International Language” (EIL) corresponds to British English (BrE), American English (AmE), Canadian English (CanE), Australian English (AusE). This is the first attempt to examine address forms in the boundaries of one language but in two different countries with their historical, cultural and political background. The aim of the paper is to study address forms in AmE and BrE and to find out the similarities and differences of their usage. This research is based on G. Hofstede’s cultural dimensions (1991), politeness theory [1, 2], Intercultural pragmatics [3, 4] and address forms theory [5, 6]. The data has been obtained through observation, questionnaires and interviews. This article represents the results of the research and analyzes the use of address forms in AmE and BrE in the situation when people need to address a stranger.

Key words: address forms, American English, British English, culture, intercultural communication.

Introduction

Taking into account the processes of globalization and intensive migration the consideration of issues of intercultural communication is becoming increasingly important. Our modern, globalized world is developing along the path of expanding the cooperation in economic, political, social and cultural life. The result of this interaction is the rapid growth of cultural exchanges and direct contacts between

state institutions, social groups and individuals of different countries and cultures. “Communication is embedded in culture, which serves as its context and is based on the prior experience of a community. In intercultural relations culture is the most important extralinguistic factor shaping its members’ communicative style and behavior” [7]. This paper investigates the sociocultural features that govern contemporary use of address forms mainly addressing a stranger focusing on similarities and differences. As the aim was to study address forms in AmE and BrE and to find out the similarities and differences of their usage, we used quantitative method, focused on gathering numerical data among Americans and Englishmen through questionnaires, descriptive research in order to describe address forms in AmE and BrE. Definitely, “culture is a system of symbol, and language is only one element of the symbolic system in this system in this network. And it is obviously that one should think of language in culture and not just of language and culture” [8]. What address forms are characteristic to the members of one culture can be totally unacceptable to the representatives of another culture. Besides, address forms reflect a vivid relationship between language and culture and show distinctive features of culture [9]. Nowadays, English is a global language [10] and the number of English speakers is growing. It’s estimated to be spoken at least to some extent by a quarter of the world’s population [11].

The term “English as an International Language” (EIL) corresponds to British English (BrE) and American English (AmE) to a smaller extent this term refers to Canadian English (CanE) and Australian English (AusE). BrE, AmE, CanE and AusE combine common features in all language levels (lexical, grammatical and phonetic) and cultural specific features. In such a context, BrE, AmE, CanE and AusE are a combination of linguistic, cultural and worldview elements that reflect the linguistic world-image of its language speaker. The cultural differences between English speakers from a wide range of linguistic and cultural backgrounds can lead to intercultural misunderstanding and miscommunication while speaking a common language like English.

Address forms in sociocultural context Address terms are an important aspect of sociolinguistic studies. “General address form is one language form which is used by people to address each other in some speech communication forms” [12]. In a speech act, address forms refer to verbal communication by the addresser and the addressee, through different channels (e.g. verbal).

The choice of address forms and expressions reflects the social relationships among people, represents the cultural connotation of a language. Polite address forms vary from culture to culture and even within different regions of a country. According to our recent study we have examined the use of address forms to a stranger in the boundaries of one language but in two different countries with their historical, cultural and political background. The choice of address terms in cross-cultural communication reflects cultural peculiarities and differences.

According to the Cultural dimensions by Geert Hofstede both Great Britain and America are on the top of the most individualistic cultures. In these countries people are motivated by their personal interests. Power distance is measured by distribution of power within a single institution or society. Both Great Britain and America are countries with a short PD (America – 40, England – 35). Such countries appreciate the equal distribution of power, equal rights and relationships. Uncertainty avoidance is the level of anxiety, the degree of discomfort experienced by the representatives of a particular culture while embarrassing situations or how they try to avoid them.

America and the United Kingdom belong to cultures with a low degree of uncertainty avoidance (the United States – 46, the United Kingdom – 35). In such cultures behavior aimed at resolving the conflict is encouraged. In such cultures, uncertainty, variability, dynamism, high mobility, tasks and problems, high tolerance for ambiguity are valued. According to Hofstede’s classification, Great Britain is a masculine country (66) and takes the 8th place out of 50, while America (62) takes the 11th place.

The values of these cultures are mutually complementary sexual roles, the stiffness of men and the softness of women, clear distribution of roles between a man and a woman. Both British and American cultures are characterized by distance and equality in communication. The interlocutors use informal norms while addressing others, so they rarely have difficulties while interacting with people (ex. Strangers). Addressing is an important component of communicative competence. In cross-cultural communication, the choice of address form reflects cultural differences. While addressing people, people evoke personal identities, create and define relationships such as close/ distant, personal/professional, peers/rank-differentiated, etc. [13]. As British people and Americans are individualistic and value equality, they try not to show differences in social status, don't show the asymmetry in age and gender.

Data and methodology In order to study address forms in AmE and BrE and to find out the similarities and differences of their usage, we used quantitative method, focused on gathering numerical data among Americans and Englishman through questionnaires, descriptive research, interviews in order to describe address forms in AmE and BrE.

The aim of the study was to analyze address forms in AmE and BrE to reveal the impact of sociocultural context on the choice of address forms while addressing a stranger in everyday communication. The questionnaire was filled by 100 informants (50 Englishman and 50 Americans), aged from 14 to 62. The collected data need further and more detailed analyses in order to get more information concerning gender, age and social differences. Besides, the aim of this paper is to focus on the preliminary results obtained, which reveal the cultural similarities and differences and modern tendencies in the usage of address forms in BrE and AmE.

Data analysis While addressing people, people evoke personal identities, create and define relationships such as close/distant, personal/professional, peers/rank-differentiated, etc. [13]. As British people are highly individualistic and value equality, they try not to show differences in social status by using special

address terms. They don't show the asymmetry in age, gender, even when they are present. Nowadays this tendency is increasingly noticeable. In the English language if one is not sure how to address the interlocutor, it is acceptable not to use any address forms at all. According to the strategy of Negative Politeness [1] the British use "attention-getters", which are generally informal: Excuse me or Hey. According to the study, the use of address terms (sir, miss, madam) has reduced greatly and it confirms anonymous style of communication, as the interlocutors don't seem necessary to name the addressee.

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